

PORTFOLIO- BASED ASSESSMENT AND THE ARGUMENTATIVE WRITING SKILLS OF GRADE 10 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

While most Filipinos are no stranger to the English language, many still need to work when it comes to putting their thoughts on paper. However, the primary concern is not just putting their thoughts, but organizing their thoughts, learning to reason out things with basis and where ideas are logically connected, unified and ruled with correct grammar. The objective of this study was to identify whether the utilization of portfolio- based assessment improved students' Argumentative writing skills in terms of cohesion, coherence and unity. Various writing opportunity was administered to find the answer to this study. This study was carried out on one group of respondents which consists of 30 students among the 123 grade 10 students. It utilized an experimental research design. Thirty (30) Grade 10 students were selected as respondents in Gloria Umali Integrated National High School during the academic year 2020-2021. Respondents were chosen through quota sampling technique. Before the treatment, a pre-test was administered to the group of respondents in order to investigate the Argumentative writing in terms of cohesion, coherence and unity of writing. Throughout the study, the experimental group was used portfolio based assessment technique. This was executed for two months followed by the post- test. The respondents were exposed to series of writing activities where the teacher provides indirect feedbacks in terms of cohesion, coherence and unity of argumentative writing. Results revealed that there is significant difference between the pre-test score and post test scores of one group of respondents as to their argumentative writing skills. This can imply that the strategy is efficient and effective in developing Argumentative writing skills.

Keywords: language, Argumentative writing skills, experimental